

PRODUCTIVE SPEECH COMPETENCE IS KEY TO JOURNALISTIC SUCCESS IN DIGITAL MEDIA ENVIRONMENT

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Annotation: *This thesis explores the development of productive speech competence among future journalists and emphasizes its vital role in succeeding in the rapidly evolving digital media sphere. The study examines how interactive technologies can enhance oral communication and written skills and prepare journalism students for effective performance in diverse media formats such as podcasts, articles, social media, and digital broadcasting. This thesis also discusses how important it is for future journalists to know English language and gives information about English for specific Purposes(ESP), ESP in journalism.*

Key words: *ELT, English for specific purposes (ESP), speech competence, productive speech, journalism, interactive technology, interactive methods*

Introduction. In today's era of advanced technology, specialists in all fields are increasingly required to know not only their native language but also at least one foreign language. This is essential for enabling professionals to engage with new innovative technologies, scientific research, and the latest developments in their respective areas. In this regard, it is worth noting that proficiency in the English language can significantly contribute to acquiring these competencies. This thesis aims to examine the significance of productive speech competence in equipping future journalists for success within the digital media landscape. It also investigates the potential of interactive technologies and contemporary pedagogical approaches in developing these essential communication skills. In addition, the research underscores the crucial role of English language education, particularly English for Specific Purposes (ESP) in journalism as an integral part of journalism training both in Uzbekistan and internationally. In this context, **productive speech competence** the ability to produce coherent, impactful spoken and written communication has become a critical skill for success in the field.

Literature review. ESP provides a framework for teaching English that is customized to the needs of particular professional areas. When applied to journalism, ESP encourages the development of language skills specifically tailored to reporting on technical, scientific, economic, or other specialized topics.(Begibaeva.F.B,2024). One effective ESP method for journalism involves targeted vocabulary and language training. Journalists undergoing ESP training can benefit from a focused approach to learning terminology and jargon relevant to their reporting beats. For instance, a

journalist covering healthcare topics would require a specialized vocabulary related to medical procedures, terminology, and scientific advancements. ESP methodologies can equip journalists with the necessary linguistic tools to convey complex information to their audience with precision and clarity. Especially, English for Specific Purposes (ESP) plays a crucial role in preparing journalism students for the specialized language and communication skills required in their field.(Begibaeva.F.B,2024).

According to Tom Hutchinson and Alan Waters(1987) ESP is just one branch of EFL/ESL, which are themselves the main branches of English Language Teaching in general. ELT, in turn is one variety of the many possible kinds of language teaching. ESP is *not* a matter of teaching' specialised varieties of English. The fact that language is used for a specific purpose does *not* imply that it is a special form of the language, different in kind from other forms. Certainly, there are some features which can be identified as "typical" of a particular context of use and which, therefore, the learner is more likely to meet in the target situation. But these differences should not be allowed to obscure the far larger area of common ground that underlies all English use, and indeed, all language use. Begibaeva (2024) and Hutchinson & Waters (1987) both stress that *English for Specific Purposes (ESP)* is an instructional approach aimed at addressing the particular communicative demands of learners in distinct professional or academic contexts. Begibaeva specifically emphasizes ESP's relevance in journalism, pointing out that focused vocabulary development and situational language practice equip aspiring journalists to accurately and effectively report on specialized areas such as healthcare, science, and economics. This field specific orientation helps journalists present complex ideas in a clear and precise manner.

When it comes to competence in speaking, one of the basic problems in foreign-language teaching is to prepare learners to be able to use the language. It is obvious that in order to be able to speak a foreign language, it is necessary to know a certain amount of grammar and vocabulary (knowlegde of language). Part of language course is therefore generally devoted to this objective. But there are other things involved in speaking (skills in speaking). Speaking indeed is not as simple as it seen. "Speaking is the *productive* skill in the oral mode. It, like the other skills, is more complicated than it seems at first and involves more than just pronouncing words" (www.linguallinks/speakingskills.htm). It needs not only physical performance but also psychological performance to be competent in speaking that is speaking in communicative and correct way. Good speaking is the combination of good flow of thinking, good micro-skills, and good psychological performance (the

absence of feeling nervous, afraid, shy, etc). The flow of thinking is the way the students organize their knowledge about the topic of discussion in a correct "sequence". The lack of knowledge and the disability of organizing the knowledge might disturb the performance of speaking. Micro-skills is the the way the students organize the features of language. (Improving students' speaking competence through small group discussion, 2010) It is also important to emphasize that *integrative technologies* and pedagogical approaches play a significant role in enhancing *productive speech skills* among future journalists. The integration of digital tools such as speech analysis software, podcast creation platforms, virtual interview simulations, and real-time feedback systems can create interactive and immersive learning environments that mirror real-world journalistic tasks.

Furthermore, *blended learning models* and *task-based learning approaches* allow students to develop speaking and writing competencies in authentic contexts, improving both fluency and communicative accuracy. These methods not only foster active language use but also encourage critical thinking, collaboration, and adaptability skills that are essential in modern journalism. Research in language education and media training supports the view that the use of integrative technologies significantly increases learner motivation, engagement, and performance in productive language tasks (Richards, 2006; Mishan & Chambers, 2010). Therefore, combining technological tools with communicative teaching strategies can greatly enhance the effectiveness of ESP instruction for journalism students.

Results and Discussions. The research conducted on the development of productive speech competence among 1st course future journalists demonstrated significant progress when integrative approaches and technologies were employed. Specifically, the use of digital tools such as virtual interview simulations, speech recording and analysis software, and online collaborative platforms contributed to improving both oral and written communication skills. Furthermore, qualitative feedback from students highlighted increased motivation and confidence in performing journalistic tasks in English, especially when practicing live reporting and interviews using multimedia tools. The results of this study affirm that integrative pedagogical approaches combined with modern digital technologies significantly enhance the productive speech skills of journalism students. The improvement in both fluency and accuracy supports Begibaeva's (2024) claim regarding the importance of ESP in equipping students with specialized vocabulary and communication strategies relevant to journalism. Interactive technologies such as virtual interview platforms and speech analysis software create authentic, immersive environments that simulate real-world journalistic situations. This hands on

experience fosters active learning and helps students transfer their skills from the classroom to practical media contexts, aligning with findings from Richards (2006) and Mishan & Chambers (2010) on the motivational benefits of technology integration in language education.

However, some students reported initial difficulties in adapting to participate speaking tasks, suggesting that while technology enhances learning, continuous practice and scaffolded support remain essential. Moreover, the balance between general English competencies and specialized ESP content is crucial to ensure that learners maintain overall communicative effectiveness, as emphasized by Hutchinson and Waters (1987). Overall, the integrative use of technology and ESP methodologies presents a promising approach to preparing future journalists for the linguistic demands of the digital media environment.

Conclusion. In conclusion, teaching English tailored to a specific profession or field requires the integration of various innovative and methodological approaches throughout the learning process, which inevitably takes time. In this regard, integrative technologies, tools, and approaches can significantly contribute to enhancing the quality of instruction. However, it is essential to know how to apply these resources appropriately and effectively. By doing so, educators can better prepare students to meet the linguistic demands of their future careers, ensuring that they develop the specialized communication skills necessary for professional success. Teaching **productive speech** which includes both speaking and writing provides journalism students with the essential communication skills needed to succeed in a dynamic and fast paced media environment. The primary benefit is that it equips future journalists with the ability to express ideas clearly, accurately, and persuasively across various platforms, whether through live interviews, news reports, podcasts, or written articles.

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